

EFFECTS OF 3D PRINTING ORIENTATION AND INFILL PATTERNS ON THE IMPACT STRENGTH AND FRACTURE BEHAVIOR OF PLA-CFRP HYBRID STRUCTURES FOR ROBOTICS

Cheonghwa Lee^{1,3}, Jun Young Choi², Sung-Hoon Ahn², Changwoo Park⁴ and Ji Ho Jeon^{1*}

¹School of Mechanical, Aerospace, and Manufacturing Engineering, University of Connecticut, Storrs, Connecticut, USA

²Department of Mechanical Engineering, Seoul National University, Seoul, 08826, South Korea

³Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, Seoul National University, Seoul, 08826, South Korea

⁴Graduate School of Engineering Practice, Seoul National University, Seoul, 08826, South Korea

**Corresponding author (jih.jeon@uconn.edu)*

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the effects of additive manufacturing parameters such as printing orientation and infill pattern on the impact resistance of polylactic acid (PLA) and carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRPs) hybrid structures. PLA was used as the filament for fused filament fabrication (FFF) to produce geometrically complex base structures, while CFRP layers were wet-layed on top of the printed PLA to reinforce the structure and enhance mechanical properties. This hybrid approach was motivated by the need to fabricate complex geometries for robotic systems using additive manufacturing, while avoiding the cost and complexity associated with large-scale composite 3D printers or tooling. Impact testing, conducted according to ASTM D4812 standards, was used to assess energy absorption. Specimens were fabricated with four distinct printing orientations (upright, on-edge, flat, and tilt) and 11 infill patterns (concentric, honeycomb, triangle, and more). Among the tested parameters, printing orientation was the dominant factor affecting impact resistance. Specimens printed in the on-edge orientation exhibited the highest impact strength, while upright specimens showed the lowest due to poor interlayer adhesion along the build direction. Infill pattern also influenced mechanical performance, with concentric and honeycomb patterns demonstrating enhanced energy dissipation and improved load distribution under impact loading. Fractographic analysis revealed brittle failure in upright specimens and interfacial delamination in on edge and flat configurations. Microscopic examination confirmed that the PLA and CFRP layers were joined primarily through mechanical interlocking. Applications of the hybrid structure to a modular mobile robotic spine component validated its effectiveness in achieving both reduced weight and impact resistant by integrating the geometric versatility of fused filament fabrication with the high strength-to-weight ratio of CFRP.

1 INTRODUCTION

In robotics, the choice of materials for robot structures is critical, as it significantly influences both the mechanical performance (e.g., strength, stiffness, density, etc.) and the efficiency of the manufacturing process (e.g., time, cost, etc.). Materials used in robot structures are broadly classified into two categories: soft materials and rigid materials [1]. Soft materials, such as polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) and rubbers, offer advantages due to their flexibility and impact-absorbing properties, making them ideal for applications that require compliance or safe human-robot interaction [2]. However, their low stiffness and limited durability restrict their use in systems requiring high load-bearing capacity, structural rigidity, or repeated performance. In contrast, rigid materials, such as aluminum, carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP), and stainless steel, are preferred for applications requiring strength, stiffness, and durability. These materials are particularly well-suited for large-scale and load-bearing systems. Aluminum is widely used in robotics compared to other metals such as stainless steel and steel, primarily

due to its cost-effectiveness, lightweight nature, and satisfactory mechanical properties. However, aluminum is still heavier than non-metallic materials (e.g., plastics, composites, etc.) and requires expensive CNC machining for manufacturing [3]. Polylactic acid (PLA) is well-known for its cost-effective and time-efficient prototyping capabilities, as well as its design flexibility. However, its applications are typically limited to small-scale systems due to its limited mechanical strength [4]. As the size of the system increases, challenges such as structural deflection, which reduces control accuracy, and a higher risk of structural failure become significant concerns. CFRP is highly effective in robot structures, particularly for applications requiring lightweight designs, suitability for large-scale systems, and high-temperature resistance. Nevertheless, their fabrication is often labor-intensive, reliant on expensive molds, and requires specialized expertise, particularly for creating structures with complex geometries [5].

Hybrid material structures with mechanical interlocking offer a promising solution by addressing the limitations of individual materials and manufacturing constraints. For mechanical material hybridization, two main categories are commonly studied: soft-rigid and rigid-rigid material hybrids. Soft-rigid material hybrids are designed to leverage the strengths of each material by utilizing rigid materials for structural support, ensuring strength and stiffness, while incorporating soft materials at connection points or contact surfaces to provide flexibility and compliance [6]. Rigid-rigid material hybrids focus on optimizing mechanical properties by combining materials with complementary characteristics. For instance, in robotic arms, CFRP is utilized to minimize weight toward the extremity (i.e., the end-effector), while metals are employed between the motor and the CFRP to ensure effective power transmission. These materials are seamlessly integrated through mechanical interlocking, enabling them to function as a unified structure and maximize the strengths of each material [7].

This study focuses on rigid-rigid material hybrid for PLA-CFRP hybrid structures, combining 3D-printed PLA with CFRP. PLA is prized for its ductility, design flexibility, and ability to form complex geometries using cost-effective 3D printing, but it lacks sufficient strength for demanding applications. In contrast, CFRP provides superior strength and an excellent strength-to-weight ratio, though its brittleness and reliance on expensive molding processes present challenges. By hybridizing these materials, the study leverages the strengths of each: PLA serves as a versatile base structure that enhances manufacturing flexibility, and its compatibility with inexpensive molds reduces overall costs for CFRP fabrication. Meanwhile, CFRP selectively reinforces areas requiring enhanced mechanical performance.

To validate the mechanical properties of PLA-CFRP hybrid materials, this research examines the impact strength and fracture behavior of PLA-CFRP composites fabricated with 11 infill patterns (aligned line; AL, adaptive cubic; AD, Archimedean chords; AR, concentric; CO, gyroid; GY, Hilbert curve; HI, honeycomb; HO, lightening; LT, Octagram spiral; OC, rectilinear; RE, triangle; TR) and four printing orientations (upright, on-edge, flat, tilt), as shown in Fig. 1(a) and 1(b) [8]. Hybrid specimens were produced by 3D-printing PLA and bonding it with CFRP layers using an epoxy-based wet layup process. Impact strength was evaluated using a Digital Izod Impact Tester (QM700A) under ASTM D4812 standards [9], and fracture behavior was analyzed [10], [11].

2 METHOD

This section outlines the key additive manufacturing parameters, including print orientation and infill pattern, as well as the method used for CFRP hybridization. Additionally, it details the fabrication procedures, specimen configurations, and testing standard employed for impact testing.

2.1 Printing Orientation

Printing orientation defines the positioning of a part relative to the Z-axis during the layer-by-layer additive manufacturing process [12]. Because bonding strength between layers along the Z-axis is generally weaker than within layers, printing orientation affects the bonding area and geometry between layers, which in turn significantly influences the mechanical performance and structural reliability of the printed components. Figure 1 presents the four printing configurations investigated in this study: upright, on edge, flat, and tilt. The Tilt orientation, ranging from 0° to 90°, was represented by a 45° angle in this work.

Figure 1: Schematic Illustration of Printing Orientations.

2.2 Infill Pattern

Infill pattern defines the internal geometry of a printed structure and is one of the most critical parameters in additive manufacturing [13]. It significantly influences not only mechanical performance but also weight, thermal behavior, and production time. As shown in Figure 2, this study investigates eleven infill patterns provided by the Bambu printer and Bambu Studio: Aligned Line (AL), Adaptive Cubic (AD), Archimedean Chords (AR), Concentric (CO), Gyroid (GY), Hilbert Curve (HI), Honeycomb (HO), Lightning (LI), Octagram Spiral (OC), Rectilinear (RE), and Triangle (TR). Some infill patterns, including AL, AD, GY, HI, RE, and TR, are influenced by printing orientation, resulting in slight variations in their internal geometry. In contrast, other patterns such as AR, CO, HO, LI, and OC remain largely unaffected by changes in printing orientation.

Figure 2: Infill Patterns by Printing Orientation.

2.3 PLA-CFRP Hybrid

The PLA-CFRP hybrid fabrication process involves two primary steps. In the first step, a PLA specimen is fabricated using additive manufacturing with a 3D printer [14]. In the second step, carbon

fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) is laid up onto the PLA substrate. The CFRP fabrication requires both a fiber reinforcement and a resin matrix, with their compositions and properties detailed in Tables 1 and 2. The fiber reinforcement used in this study is a high-density 3K plain-woven carbon fabric (240 g/m², 1040 mm width, 0.30 mm thickness), making it ideal for manual lay-up processes [15]. The resin consists of RESOLTECH Epoxy System 1050 with 1056S hardener (100:35 weight ratio), exhibiting low viscosity, good deaeration, and high mechanical performance through ambient and post-curing, with a TG of up to 66.7°C and Shore D hardness above 90 [16].

Table 1: Fiber Specification.

Category	Specification
Fiber Type	Carbon Fiber
Tow Size	3K (3,000 filaments per tow)
Weave Type	Plain Weave
Areal Weight	240 g/m ²
Thickness	0.30 mm

Table 2: Resin Specification.

Category	Specification
Epoxy	RESOLTECH Epoxy System 1050
Hardener	1056S
Mixing Ratio (by weight)	100 : 35 (Resin : Hardener)
Mixed Viscosity (23°C)	462 mPa·s
Gel Time (70 g at 23°C)	Approximately 37 minutes
Full Cure (Room Temperature)	14 days (TG: 49.1°C, Shore D Hardness: 89)

3 RESULTS

This section presents and validates the experimental results on impact strength, fracture behavior, and microstructural characterization of the interfacial region in the PLA-CFRP hybrid structure.

3.1 Impact Testing

Figure 3 presents the impact strength results as a function of printing orientation and infill pattern. Subfigures 3(a) to 3(d) correspond to PLA specimens fabricated in upright, on-edge, flat, and tilt orientations, respectively. The results indicate that printing orientation has a more pronounced effect on impact strength than infill pattern. Specimens printed in the upright orientation exhibited the lowest strength due to weak interlayer bonding, while the on-edge orientation showed the highest strength, as the layers were aligned perpendicular to the impact direction, thereby requiring more energy to initiate fracture. Flat and tilt orientations demonstrated intermediate performance, with the tilt orientation slightly outperforming the flat configuration. Among infill patterns, concentric and honeycomb designs provided relatively higher impact resistance, particularly in the on-edge orientation. However, their overall influence remained secondary to that of the printing orientation.

Figure 3(e) and 3(f) show the impact strength results for PLA-CFRP hybrid specimens fabricated in flat and tilt orientations. The results indicate that the overall trend related to printing parameters remains consistent with those observed in PLA-only specimens. Specifically, there is minimal difference in impact strength between flat and tilt orientations, and the effect of infill pattern is relatively insignificant in both cases. However, the application of CFRP reinforcement results in a substantial enhancement in impact resistance, with hybrid specimens exhibiting improvements of at least fivefold and up to tenfold compared to their PLA-only counterparts.

Figure 3: Impact Strength by Printing Orientation and Infill Pattern. (a) PLA upright. (b) PLA on edge. (c) PLA flat. (d) PLA tilt. (e) PLA-CFRP hybrid flat. (f) PLA-CFRP hybrid tilt.

3.2 Fracture Behavior

Figure 4 illustrates the fracture behavior of specimens with the rectilinear (RE) infill pattern across various printing orientations. In PLA-only samples, the upright, on edge, and flat orientations exhibited relatively brittle fractures with straight, vertically aligned cracks, primarily due to stress concentration along interlayer planes. In contrast, the tilt orientation showed more complex fracture surfaces with irregular crack paths following the rectilinear infill, indicating increased energy absorption and crack

deflection. Although the PLA-CFRP hybrid composites demonstrated significantly higher impact strength than the PLA-only specimens, their fracture behavior followed similar trends across printing orientations and infill configurations.

Figure 4: Fracture Behavior with Rectilinear (RE) Infill Pattern.

3.3 Microscopic Image

Figure 5 presents microscopic images of the interlocking surfaces formed at the interface between the PLA and CFRP in hybrid materials. In each image, the upper dark region corresponds to the CFRP layer, while the lower greenish region represents the 3D-printed PLA structure. All images were captured at the same magnification (scale bar = 500 μm) to facilitate direct comparison of the microstructural morphology and deposition patterns. Across all infill patterns, well-developed mechanical interlocking was observed, with minor micro voids confined to the CFRP bulk and no visible cracks. As these voids were away from the interface, bonding remained strong, contributing to improved interfacial adhesion and structural integrity.

Figure 5: Microscopic Image of Interlocking Surfaces in PLA-CFRP Hybrids.

4 ROBOTICS APPLICATIONS

Figure 6 illustrates the overall fabrication process and final implementation of the proposed PLA-CFRP hybrid structure for robotic frame applications. The entire process consists of three main stages: (1) fabrication of a PLA core frame via 3D printing, (2) manual lamination of fiber and resin to form the CFRP shell frame, and (3) integration of the hybrid structure into a mobile robotic platform. This hybrid design approach, combining additive manufacturing and composite lamination, enables design flexibility, manufacturing efficiency, and improved mechanical performance, making it a promising strategy for developing next-generation robotic frames with complex functions and robust structural integrity.

Figure 6: Fabrication Process and Robotic Integration of the PLA-CFRP Hybrid Spine Structure.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This study comprehensively evaluated the influence of 3D printing orientation and infill pattern on the mechanical behavior of PLA-CFRP hybrid structures. Impact tests identified printing orientation as the most critical factor affecting toughness and fracture characteristics, with the on-edge orientation delivering the highest impact resistance due to improved interlayer bonding, while the upright orientation exhibited the lowest performance. Among various infill patterns, concentric, honeycomb, and triangle patterns consistently showed enhanced impact strength, particularly in on-edge and flat orientations. Microscopic analysis demonstrated that mechanical interlocking at the interface, strengthened interfacial bonding and mitigated delamination. The observed fracture modes varied significantly with printing orientations, underscoring the crucial role of structural configuration in optimizing hybrid performance. The developed PLA-CFRP hybrid was successfully implemented as the central spine in a modular mobile robot, validating its applicability for lightweight, high-strength robotic components. Future work will extend to dynamic loading assessments, fatigue behavior analysis, and further optimization of multi-material interfaces to enhance the durability and functionality of hybrid structures.

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